

target CRM	Mg	Cu	Co	Ge	Cu	Ga	In	Co	Cu	Ni	V	REE	P	P		
application/waste flow	Al dross (D 03 04*, D 03 08*) - this waste flow results from Al smelting and fluxing. The latter only applies to secondary Al smelting. Primary dross is almost always processed to recover Al and is not really considered as waste.	Lead slag (D 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Lead slag (D 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Lead slag (D 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Zn sludges (D 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy	Zn sludges (D 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy	Zn sludges (D 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy	Cu slags (D 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy	Cu slags (D 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy	Cu slags (D 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy	Steel slags from BOF (D 02 02)	Red mud (D 09 03)	Other biomass ash (excluding wood ash and agricultural waste ash, which only have low concentrations of P) (D 01 15, B, D 01 17, B)	Sewage sludge ashes (bottom ash: D 01 02, fly ash: D 01 14) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of municipal sewage sludge, which is already a waste, and cannot be considered as a product		
Treatment scenario without CRM recovery (Partial) existing or potential treatment scenario with CRM recovery	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Treatment, then used as aggregate N.A.	Treatment, then landfill N.A.	Landfill Application of (typically untreated) biomass ashes to forest/soil	Landfill Direct use of the ashes as soil improver or used in the production of fertilizer		
Nb. Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?															
design/input-specific criteria																
1.1 Dissipation and heterogeneity in product/waste flow (accumulation and mass fraction within a product/waste flow)	How dissipated is the CRM and/or the CRM containing application in the product? Is the CRM and/or CRM containing application accumulated in specific components? Is the CRM accumulated/enriched in parts of the waste flow or is it more widely distributed within the waste flow? How is the CRM mass fraction in relation to the ore grade (in the application/component/product/parts of the waste flow)?	Homogeneously distributed in the dross	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed in the slags	Homogeneously distributed as oxide in the ashes (Falk et al., 2023).		
1.2 Change in product design/input (changes in quantities, replacements, etc.)	What are the current developments regarding change in product design, especially change in CRM quantities and replacements? Are there expected input changes that will affect the waste flow?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	P in biomass ashes results from its presence in the tissues of plants and animals. P is in adenosine triphosphate (ATP), animal bones and excreta. When these are burnt, it is concentrated. The concentration in these sources and their ashes is therefore not expected to change, but could change in ashes that arise from combustion of mixtures of these materials.	The ash is a product of municipal sewage management. The concentration of P in the ashes is not expected to change as long as P is not precipitated prior to or during the wastewater treatment. Besides, due to its chemical stability, the mass of P per dry ash unit remains almost constant. The ashes have to be treated to recover P as a product (Herzel et al., 2016; Egle et al., 2023; Luyckx & Canevhem, 2020).		
1.3 Product information and labelling (identifiability of CRM containing applications and components)	Does the product labelling provide sufficient information about the mass fraction and location of CRM in the product? Is there a required or voluntary labelling?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable		
waste flow-specific criteria																
2.1 Dissipation in waste flow	How high is the mass fraction of the CRM in the (collected) waste flow (in relation to the ore grade)? How is the CRM containing application collected (e.g. application-, component-, product-level, mixed with other products)? Is there a pre-sorting regarding input material/parts of the waste flow?	Primary dross: 8 wt% on average, sometimes up to 15 wt% Secondary dross: 3-3 wt%	0.6-0.8 wt%, sometimes up to 1.4 wt%	0.04 wt% on average, sometimes up to 0.6 wt%	16.8 ppm on average	0.6 wt% on average	160 ppm	209 ppm	500-1800 ppm	0.007-0.008 wt%	150-2000 ppm	Variable, up to 2-3% V in some cases (Saron et al., 2020)	Total REE content is below 1 wt%	P in biomass ash from meat and bone meal and poultry litter can be in the range of the concentration of P in phosphate rock. P in biomass ash is mostly in the mineral hydroxyapatite, which is dispersed within the ash. There is no pre-sorting - often the biomass fuels are burnt as mixtures (Leng, 2019).	Consistent homogeneous waste flow, the average P content in sewage sludge ashes is 9.4 wt% (dry matter) (Barnes et al., 2016). Economic recovery requires > 9 wt%, < 6 wt% is economically nonviable (LBA, 2019).	
2.2 Mineralogical state	In which mineralogical state is the CRM in the application or waste flow (e.g. metal, oxide, etc.)?	Alloy	Matte (sulphide) or oxide	Metallic or oxide	Metallic or oxide	Metallic or oxide	Metallic or oxide	Metallic or oxide	Metallic or oxide	Metallic or oxide	Metallic, oxide or sulphide	Metallic or oxide	Oxide	Oxide	Hydroxyapatite Ca5(PO4)3(OH) Whitlockite (Ca9(Mg,Fe)PO4)6PO3(OH), an endmember of the mineral phase (Ca3-xMg,Fe)2(PO4)2, is the primary phosphorus carrier in sewage sludge ashes (Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013; Herzel et al., 2021; Kaina et al., 2023).	
2.3 Product and/or component collection (collection and return rates)	How high are the collection and return rates? Why are they high/low?	High	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Approximately 56.4% of the generated ashes were landfilled in the EU in 2022 (or got lost by co-incineration), 43.5% were available for P recovery. Due to legislative requirements, changes are anticipated in the future. It can be assumed that the proportion of mono-incineration will increase.	
2.4 Current waste generated	Which waste quantities are currently generated?	2.75 Mt	0.76 Mt	0.76 Mt	0.76 Mt	152 Mt	152 Mt	152 Mt	4.88 Mt	4.88 Mt	4.88 Mt	10 Mt (Applying the ratios of Piemont et al., 2021, to Eurofer, 2020)	7.43 Mt	2021: All biomass 2.2 Mt/a; Other biomass (animal waste) bottom ash 165 kt/a; Other biomass (animal waste) fly ash 97.3 kt/a [not included in the comments in this column because of low P content are: Woody biomass bottom ash 196 kt/a; Woody biomass fly ash 116 kt/a; Agri residue (plant) bottom ash 100 Mt/a; Agri residue (plant) fly ash]	31.3% of all sewage sludge is incinerated, producing 929 kt of ash in the EU, based on EUROSTAT and national reports.	
2.5 Future waste generated	Which waste quantities are expected to be generated in the future?	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant or slight increase	Constant	2050: All biomass 2.5 Mt/a; Other biomass (animal waste) bottom ash 124 kt/a; Other biomass (animal waste) fly ash 73 kt/a; [Not included in the comments in this column because of low P content are: Woody biomass bottom ash 175 kt/a; Woody biomass fly ash 103 kt/a; Agri residue (plant) bottom ash 1.26 Mt/a; Agri residue (plant) fly ash]	Sewage sludge production remains stable, however, incineration is expected to increase by 2050.	
3.1 Availability of identification technology for CRM containing application/material/component/product	Is there a technology to identify the CRM containing application/component/product to enable its recovery?	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	Yes, established techniques (e.g., XRF)	In-line P measurement with XRF is possible (e.g., Huskova et al., 2014, but probably not useful in a typical facility that consistently processes ashes from the same source (with the same composition)).	Yes, but not in-line (batch characterisation).
3.2 Manual removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Is it possible to manually remove the CRM containing application or material from the product/waste flow (is it screwed, glued, welded)?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	P is homogeneously distributed in a fine powder (Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013) --> only chemical processes or direct use	
3.3 Automated removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Are processes available to remove the CRM containing application/component by automation? What is its TRL level?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	P is homogeneously distributed in a fine powder (Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013) --> only chemical processes or direct use	
3.4 Identifiability and separability of CRM containing material after liberation	Is it possible to identify and sort the CRM containing materials after liberation (e.g. shredding)? This can be without preceding removal/sorting or after preceding removal.	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Heavy metals cannot be removed easily. The low solubility of heavy metals and their incorporation into the ash matrix present significant challenges, necessitating complex and energy-demanding methods for their removal (Adam et al., 2009; Donatello & Cheeseman, 2013).	

target CRM application/waste flow	Mg	Cu	Co	Ge	Cu	Ga	In	Co	Cu	Ni	V	REE	P	P
Al dross (D 03 04*, D 03 08*) - this waste flow results from Al smelting and fluxing. The latter only applies to secondary Al smelting. Primary dross is almost always processed to recover Al and is not really considered as waste.	Lead slag (D 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Lead slag (D 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Lead slag (D 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Lead slag (D 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Zn sludges (D 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy.	Zn sludges (D 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy.	Zn sludges (D 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy.	Cu slags (D 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy.	Cu slags (D 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy.	Cu slags (D 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy.	Steel slags from BOF (D 02 02)	Red mud (D 09 03)	Other biowaste ash (excluding wood ash and agricultural waste ash, which only have low concentrations of P) (D 01 15, B, D 01 17, B)	Sewage sludge ashes (bottom ash: D 01 02, fly ash: D 01 14) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of municipal sewage sludge, which is already a waste, and cannot be considered as a product.
Treatment scenario without CRM recovery	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then used as aggregate	Treatment, then landfill	Landfill	Landfill
(Partial) existing or potential treatment scenario with CRM recovery	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	Application of (typically untreated) biomass ashes to forest/soil	Direct use of the ashes as soil improver or used in the production of fertilizer
Nb. Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?													
3.5 Ability to concentrate CRM containing material / mechanically remove impurities	Is it possible to concentrate or to mechanically remove impurities from the CRM containing material flow?													
3.6 Ability to thermally and/or chemically separate and refine CRMs from concentrates	Is there a thermal and/or chemical recovery technology for the CRM? What is its TRL level?													
4.1 Market and quality of 2CRM	Is there a market for the 2CRM? What is the quality of the 2CRM compared to the primary one? How volatile is the market?													
4.2 Price competition of 2CRM with primary	Would it be cheaper to use the waste flow instead of an ore to recover the CRM?													
4.3 Economic incentives	Do specific economic incentives exist (tax related, fees, etc.) to recover the CRM? Are there other materials or elements driving the recovery?													
4.4 Economically viable case studies	Are there (potentially) economically viable case studies for the recovery of the CRM? Does the value or the quantity of the CRM play a decisive role?													
4.5 Recycling conflicts with other materials or elements (especially more valuable ones)	Is there a recycling conflict with other materials or elements, especially with more valuable ones in the product/waste flow?													
environmental criteria														
5.1 Logistics and infrastructure	How are the logistic and infrastructure requirements for the recovery process (process steps, distances, etc.)? Can existing infrastructure be used?													
5.2 Energy and chemical requirements for separation and sorting	What are the energy and chemical requirements for mechanical separation and sorting?													
5.3 Energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or chemical recovery	What are the energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or (bio)chemical recovery in comparison with primary production?													
5.4 Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	Is there a recycling conflict with hazardous substances? Are there hazardous substances in the respective application/waste flow? Will there be hazardous substances liberated during the recovery process? Can the hazardous substances be contained adequately?													
5.5 Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the 2CRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?													

target CRM	Mg	Cu	Co	Ge	Cu	Ga	In	Co	Cu	Ni	V	REE	P	P	
application/waste flow	Al dross (f0 03 04*, f0 03 08*) - this waste flow results from Al smelting and fluxing. The latter only applies to secondary Al smelting. Primary dross is almost always processed to recover Al and is not really considered as waste.	Lead slag (f0 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Lead slag (f0 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Lead slag (f0 04 01*) - this waste flow results from lead metallurgy.	Zn sludges (f1 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy	Zn sludges (f1 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy	Zn sludges (f1 02 02*) - this waste flow result from zinc metallurgy	Cu slags (f0 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy	Cu slags (f0 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy	Cu slags (f0 06 01) - this waste results from Cu metallurgy	Steel slags from BOF (f0 02 02)	Red mud (f1 09 03)	Other biowaste ash (excluding wood ash and agricultural waste ash, which only have low concentrations of P) (f0 01 15_B, f0 01 17_B)	Seaweed sludge ashes (bottom ash: f9 01 02, fly ash: f9 01 14) - this waste flow results from the thermal treatment of municipal sewage sludge, which is already a waste, and cannot be considered as a product	
Treatment scenario without CRM recovery	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then landfill	Treatment, then used as aggregate	Treatment, then landfill	Landfill	Landfill	
(Partially) existing or potential treatment scenario with CRM recovery	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	Application of (typically untreated) biomass ashes to forest/soil	Direct use of the ashes as soil improver or used in the production of fertilizer	
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?													
legal criteria															
6.1	Recovery targets	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No, the standard in EU member states is the direct utilisation of sewage sludges on the ground (except in Germany, Austria and Switzerland, where national regulations impose certain requirements for the P recovery from sewage sludge (e.g. German ordinance on the Reorganisation of Sewage Sludge Utilisation, AbfKlärV with a P-content threshold and the P recovery is mandatory from 2029 on).
6.2	Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM containing application?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
6.3	Legal incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No, except in Germany, Austria and Switzerland, recovery of P is mandatory.
6.4	End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for 2CRM?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No, but the inclusion of calcium phosphate from sewage sludge ash in the EU Fertiliser Regulation is currently under discussion (EU 2025/973).

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Copper Scrap Regulation (EU) No 715/2013 Commission Regulation (EU) No 715/2013 of 25 July 2013 establishing criteria determining when Cu scrap ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council

Landfill Directive 1999/31/EC Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste

Metal Scrap Regulation (EU) No 333/2011 Council Regulation (EU) No 333/2011 of 31 March 2011 establishing criteria determining when certain types of scrap metal cease to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council

Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives

- Abbreviations used**
- BOF Basic Oxygen Furnace
 - CRM Critical Raw Material
 - EAF Electric Arc Furnace
 - EU European Union
 - LIBS Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
 - PGM Platinum Group Metal
 - REE Rare Earth Elements
 - TRL Technology Readiness Level
 - XRF X-ray fluorescence
 - XRT X-ray transmission